

Airbus Defence and Space high speed cross atmospheric optical comms program

DEFENCE AND SPACE

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Ludovic BLARRE

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AIRBUS

Optical Feeder Links for the VHTS Mission

Main objective:

- Reduce the cost per bit
- Increase Max system capacity

Main requirements:

- Bidirectional
- High Availability (99,9%)
- High Capacity (1Tbps)

TELEO Optical communication demo mission

Telecom links (Exail transceiver):

10Gbauds OOK Uplink
10Gbauds DPSK Downlink

Power monitoring capability:

Uplink received irradiance:
20dB range, ~1kHz

Uplink injected power:
20dB range, 20kHz

TELEO status & main features

Key milestones:

Project start – **September 2020**

Full payload delivery to AIT – **February 2023**

Launch date – **27th May 2023**

DADR-8 Arrival at final orbit – **24th September 2023**

TELEO SW upload – **October 2023**

Commissioning – **Mid-October 2023**

First IOT – **End November 2023**

On-board optical payload SWaP:

Total mass is **86 kg**

Instrument is **< 80x60x60 cm³**

Power consumption is **280 W (OP)** and 130 W (NOP)

TELEO optical payload

TELEO optical payload on Badr-8

Test of telecom physical link:

1. Pointing budget (PAT)
2. Ground-Satellite link budget (static gain)
3. Error correction code (Interleaver / FEC)

Test of various ground stations & sites:

1. Test efficiency of technical solutions (AO / Pre-compensation)
2. Test different sites conditions (atmospheric conditions)
3. Collect atmospheric data (time series)
4. Validation of atmospheric canal (models)

Teide (Tenerife)
ADS-NL

Obs. Côte d'Azur (Nice)
Fr-OGS

Francazal (Toulouse)
ONERA

A-OGS ground station at ESA Tenerife facility

A-OGS composed of ESA OGS telescope, CARO adaptive optics bench and Airbus Netherlands beacons subsystems for TELEO demo Part 1

Airbus 10Gbauds digital Ground Communication Chain

CE318-TL9 photometer from CIMEL Electronique SAS

Sky InSight™ from Reuniwatt

Three main application for ground to GEO optical links

MILSATCOMM

- TOP-M
- 10-100 Gbps Class
- 10G/λ - OOK
- Various
- COMPLEX

CLOUD MIGRATION

- TOP-M/L
- Tbps Class
- 100G/λ DP-QPSK
- Time tolerant
- SIMPLE

FEEDER

- TOP-L
- Tbps Class
- 100G/λ QPSK
- Realtime
- COMPLEX

Airbus portfolio to cover all Optical Coms verticals

